

ANALYSIS OF CHILDREN'S DRAWINGS OF BALINESE FOLKLORE

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Abstract

Bali is a small island with many different arts and cultures. One of its assets is its folklore which needs to be preserved as an educational resource. The current era of globalization has raised concerns about the extinction of this traditional knowledge. This article presents the analysis of children's drawings of Balinese folklore. It explores the question: What are the benefits of drawing folklore for children's growth, artistic and moral development? The research uses an art research method conducting a comprehensive analysis of 48 children's drawings of Balinese folklore themes. It was found that drawing folklore allowed children to be more spontaneous and authentic which can have an impact on their growth and creativity. Artistic expression also varied with region and gender.

Keywords: Analysis, Balinese folklore, children's drawing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional folklore is represented in classical forms; in signs, figures, traditional texts, and performing arts (Abidin & Razak, 2003). Folklore scholars are attracted to exploring its deeper meaning (Hughes, 2012). Folk art was analyzed and the genre was

changed from an oral to a visual tradition (Hauser, 2002).

In Bali, there are around 61 folk tales (Suwija, et al., 2019). These have been passed down from one generation to the next in the oral tradition. On February 4, 2023, a competition at the Bali Province level was held, judging

children's images of Balinese folklore. The humor, authenticity, and simplicity of the drawings inspired the author's research.

The history of children's painting in Sayan Village, Ubud, Bali was reviewed by Jane Belo (1933). In the same era, Walter Spies and Rudolf Bonnet influence Balinese paintings. Margaret Mead and Gregory Bateson collected around 2000 paintings, both by children and adult Balinese artists. In 1959, Arie Smit painted with Penestanan children, with extraordinary results which made residents there and in the surrounding villages prosperous (Lim, 1983). Spurred by the above phenomenon, the author has researched children's painting and folklore since 2019. His focus has been on the villages of Penestanan, Penglipuran Bangli, and Denpasar (Karja, 2019; 2022; 2023).

What are the benefits and significance of Balinese folklore in the development of children? To answer this question, the author conducted research by analyzing 48 children's drawings with the theme of Balinese folklore.

2. METHOD

This research uses an art research approach by using works of art as research objects. Leavy (2023) stated that the process of artistic practice itself can become research. He further explained that art can be used as research data. In the view of Davis, W. (2022) the method reflects the history of art, aesthetics, and the psychology of perception. As material objects, folklore images become sources of information. This art-based research aims to understand and interpret empirical phenomena in the relationship between images as expressions of fine art and folklore, which have a system of logic, aesthetic ethics, and truth values.

This research was undertaken using a sample of 48 Balinese folklore images from several different stories, obtained from the competition mentioned above. The research sample represented children from Badung, Tabanan, Gianyar, Klungkung, and Denpasar City Regencies. The author observed the children using these steps without instruction: 1) mental preparation, sitting, and thinking. 2) sketching using pencil and eraser 3) adding color to cover the surface of the paper. Here the color often followed the representative

color, e.g. sky is blue, tree is green 4) finishing by checking and controlling the whole surface of the drawing 5) visualizing the story.

From the 48 drawings, the five best were selected, and are presented below with their corresponding folktale. In the Observation and Analysis section, the five drawings will be discussed.

3. BALINESE FOLKLORE AND DRAWINGS

Five Balinese folktales are presented in this paper. These are the most popular stories among children. Each folktale is briefly described so that the reader understands the significance of each drawing.

3.1 The Mandara Giri Rotation

The Mandara Giri Rotation is part of the classic Mahabharata story where gods and giants must work together to find Tirta Amrita, holy water. The Turtle is at the bottom of the sea, and Lord Indra is at the top of the mountain. Naga Basuki has been tied to the top of the mountain by the gods and giants. The gods and giants rotate the Mandara mountain in the

milky sea of Ksiarnawa. When the mountain is turned, a pitch-black liquid comes out which Lord Shiva drinks and his neck turns blue from the poison. Then, the mountain releases Tirta Amrita, the holy water. The giants try to take it, but Lord Vishnu persuades them not to. Tirta Amrita holy water is then distributed among humans in order to bring happiness and peace.

Figure 1. Drawing by I Putu Krishna Nanda Permana (Klungkung), The gods and giants rotate Mandara Giri. (Photo taken by the author, 2023).

3.2 The Bali Strait Legend

This legend has cultural significance for the Balinese people, because they believe it explains the separation of the islands of Bali and Java. The legend tells the story of Mpu Sidhimantra, a Brahmin, and his son Manik Angkeran who has a gambling habit. He seeks help from his father, who in turn, asks the gods for help.

The gods direct him to Naga Besakih, who leads Mpu Sidhimantra to the treasure. However, Manik Angkeran, the son, driven by greed, steals the treasure from Naga Besakih and has to face dire consequences, it looked like he was dead. Mpu Sidhimantra begs Naga Besakih for his son to be brought back to life. Naga Besakih agrees, on the condition that Mpu Sidhimantra help him solve a problem. To prevent his son from leaving Bali and crossing into Java to gamble, Mpu Sidhimantra creates the Bali Strait. .

Figure 2. Drawing by Aisyah Dzakira Khanza, Denpasar. Mpu Sidi Mantra makes the boundary that becomes the Bali Strait for his son, Manik Angkeran. (Photo taken by the author, 2023).

3.3 Cangak Meketu

In a tale from Lake Kumudasara, a crane named Cangak Meketu disguises himself as a priest to deceive and eat the fish in the pond. However, his plan backfires when the last resident, a clever crab, asks to be placed on the stork's neck instead of its feet. Seizing the opportunity, the crab strangles the heron to death.

Figure 3. Drawing by Ni Ketut Nayla Natasha Anjani Gunawan (Denpasar) The stork gets ready to take the fish with the mind of a holy priest. (Photo taken by the author, 2023).

3.4 Ketimun Emas

In the folktale of Golden Ketimun, a brave girl faces the threat of an evil green giant who is after her to capture and eat her.

Figure 4. Drawing by Dzikra Khaliqah Al Fathinah (Denpasar), Being carried away by a giant. (Photo taken by the author, 2023).

3.5 Rajapala

Rajapala, a young hunter, was resting by a lake and met seven angels bathing. He steals one of the angel's clothes and will only return it in exchange for her marriage. The two then have a son named Durma. The angel returns to heaven and leaves Rajapala to raise their son. When Durma grows up, he meets a giant demon. The demon kidnaps Durma.

Figure 5. Drawing by Putu Radika Deandra Arcelia, Denpasar. Rajapala (Photo was taken by the author, 2023).

4. OBSERVATION AND ANALYSIS

In the first drawing of the Mandara Giri Rotation, the composition of the painting is focused in the middle, with three demons on the right side and three Gods on the left side expresses their power to rotate the Mandara Mountain (Fig. 1). The drawing was influenced by the Kamasan style of painting which is based on classical Balinese style. The skill of these children is more advanced in terms of

expressing line, form, color, and composition.

In the drawing of the Bali Strait Legend (Fig.2), the girl draws the wave and priest very expressively. The painting skill is highly developed playing with form and color nuances, in the naturalistic style and based on real life.

The drawing of a bird with a crown was inspired by the third folktale. The bird represents the crane, and has a sun-filled aura with beautiful color gradations and nuances (fig.3). This symbolizes its deceptive intention to capture the fish. The story warns of greed and deception, celebrated through artistic expression, and highlights the wisdom of the humble and resourceful crab. The drawing was influenced by Ubud's style of painting. The drawing shows the high skill of choosing and playing with color nuances.

Figure 4 was inspired by the brave girl Ketimun Mas of the folktale, who runs desperately to avoid the giant. The expressions of both characters are well depicted, the girl showing fear and the giant exuding menace. The colors in the background effectively set the scene, enhancing the overall impact of the artwork.

Despite her efforts, the girl remains unable to escape the giant's grasp, her emotion depicted by the tears of pain and fear streaming down her face. The animals around her, including the chicken, the cat, and her parents, are shown in a state of panic as they witness the unfolding drama. The artist skillfully captures the intensity of the scene, making the characters come alive and conveying the urgency of the girl's plight as she tries to escape the clutches of the menacing green giant. This artwork captures every detail of emotion skillfully.

The fifth folktale of Rajapala (fig.5) is a common theme in the arts of Bali, not only among children's drawings but also among senior traditional artists. The Rajapala folktale is seen in different visual expressions such as relief, painting, and sculpture, including performing arts such as theater and traditional drama.

In Figure 5 above, the drawing of Rajapala shows the authenticity of the artist expressing their skills without the influence of any tradition. This drawing is very unique in composition, perspective, humor, and naïvete which makes the drawing come to life.

Even though Bali is a small island, there are many variations in local

traditions and regional characteristics. It follows that there is a diversity of painting styles in Bali. The Klungkung area is more classical Balinese painting, influenced by Kamasan painting which tends to be related to wayang/puppet images and coloring techniques typical of the region. Pita Maha style is a Balinese modern style influenced by Western art, Batuan, Ubud, and Sanur styles; Penestenan young artists style; Pengosekan flora and fauna style; miniature Keliki style; and the general academic style based on the Western system.

Children's art is influenced by their environment (Lim, 1983; Karja, 2019; 2023). Children from Denpasar, the capital city, are exposed to many modern aspects and are heavily influenced by books, YouTube videos, and other media. This is reflected in their art, which is different from children from other regions.

In the Gianyar region, traditional arts have been well developed like in areas of Batuan village and the Ubud area. For example, the art that originated in Pengosekan Village of flora and fauna has distinctive forms and techniques. Children from Tabanan are different again, namely, they are less influenced by traditional art and their expressions are freer

and more spontaneous.

There were striking differences between boys and girls in their aesthetic and emotional expression. The research revealed that in general, boys tended to be more focused on creating exact or natural shapes, whereas girls emphasized their sense of sensitivity in selecting and using colors. Of course, gender alone may not account for these differences, and they may be related to age, environmental factors, and region of origin.

5. DISCUSSION

Drawing is a creative process that can awaken children's potential. Imagination and fantasy become an important part of the development and growth of children's souls. When drawing these folk stories without restriction, children were free to express themselves purely and honestly. The aspect of play emerged as an important part of the drawing process. This is seen in Figure 5. With spontaneity and without much thought of the natural forms around them, children steadily drew based on the objects from the stories they had heard, seen, and imagined.

The children chose which stories would be discussed and they drew what they liked. As they drew, their enthusiasm and concentration increased. They took the content of the story very seriously.

The choices that the children made while drawing reflected their developmental level. Children spontaneously drew in bright primary colors of red, yellow, and blue. This was followed by secondary colors. Some children played with shades of color with interesting gradations. Generally, in children over seven years of age, shapes begin to be influenced by traditional painting forms and nature, and they tend to begin to lead to a naturalistic style of art (fig.2 and 3). Textures were created with incisions that make neat contour lines. The composition and balance of their art was unique as a result of their freedom of artistic expression.

These folktales can provide important lessons for the psyche and mentality of children. Apart from being entertainment, these stories can also arouse the sensitivity and awareness of children's souls, leading to their moral development.

Emmanuel Kant (Suyata, 2011) has long recognized the importance of

moral teaching in the world of education and it has long been the philosophical basis of the character-building process of children in schools.

Through the art of drawing Balinese folklore in schools, character education is fostered in an integrated manner. Thus, it could be said that drawing folklore could have much potential for the development of children's personalities.

Attitudes worth emulating are instilled with practice and expression of emotion in the visual representation of these folktales. For example, the children are exposed to antagonistic and protagonist, good versus evil, which are key concepts in Balinese culture.

Education should be used to build children's culture in a civilizing process (Suda, 2018). Drawing folktales contributes significantly to children's learning, development, creativity, and imagination.

Viktor Lowenfeld was born in Austria and was a professor of art education at Pennsylvania State University. His ideas influenced many art educators in the post-war United States. In particular, he emphasized how children at different stages of

artistic development should be stimulated with appropriate media and themes, and curriculum should be guided by developmental considerations. Lowenfeld (1957) described six stages of artistic development.

Of these six stages, two points are relevant to this art-based research and are apply to the ages of the children sampled. At the fourth stage of artistic development described by Lowenfeld, that of Dawning Realism (7-9 years), children begin to become more critical of their work. At this stage it becomes clear that a structured sequence for drawing objects is no longer adequate. Although schemes are still used to create drawings, they are more complex than the schemes used in the previous stage. The fifth, 10-13 years of age, is called the pseudo-naturalistic stage, the use of values and light is now visible in pictures. Children at this stage of artistic development are highly critical of their success. Success is determined by the degree of realism achieved in the picture. Although sometimes there is a feeling of frustration when you are unable to capture the desired shape. The child's way with line and color, his sense of form, and the expressiveness of his words and gestures demanded an explanation (Ecker, 1973).

Balinese folklore is generally classified as fables and uses animal traits to teach ethical and moral teachings, such as the essence of learning how to live together. This is relevant to how children interact and behave in society, for example, learning good and bad manners.

Children learn how to appreciate folklore by visualizing and verbalizing the stories, focusing on the form and expression which leads to getting the essence of the story, and its wider and deeper meaning, and tapping into the ancient wisdom of Balinese culture.

The fusion of art practice and visualization of folklore encourages children to practice making better drawings and paintings. An additional possible benefit is that children build the capacity to become storytellers.

Balinese folklore in the global era of today appeals to a larger audience having wider exposure. Participants in the study were not only from Bali to but also children from other islands were interested in Balinese folklore. That implies that having Balinese folklore as a drawing activity helps to spread and preserve Balinese art and culture.

The creative process involved in

the transformation of traditional oral stories into visual art can be an important part of early childhood education. Drawing attention to the process can develop children's reflective thinking about social life (Agbenyega, Tamakloe, & Klibthong, 2017).

Balinese folklore was traditionally an oral tradition but in recent times, the stories have been written down and illustrated in children's storybooks. They have been made into comics, with representative photos, videos, and movies. These books are also published using children's illustrations. These are becoming increasingly popular along with the development of information technology.

As a result of this study, the author has taught more classes about drawing folklore and story-telling to university students and the community in general.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, from the analysis of Balinese folklore children's drawings, it was seen that children from different regions draw differently, and girls and boys emphasize different aspects of artistic expression. Children

were focused and motivated while drawing. They were interested in learning about Balinese folklore and absorbed traditional values and morals from this activity, as well as general logic and aesthetics. While drawing folklore, children developed drawing skills and the stories allowed children to be authentic, playful, and flowing in their expression, which has an impact on their creativity, hopefully beyond this activity. The author hopes that this article will become a reference in learning to draw for children, studying Balinese folklore, or the folklore of their country. and learning to tell stories.

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